

Controlled Perturbation Algorithms for Saddle Point Escape of Generic Non-convex Optimization Problems (Algorithm Description – Version 1.1)

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Abstract

We introduce the Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (CPA) for escaping saddle points in generic *deterministic* non-convex optimization problems. CPA uses two gradient evaluations per iteration, which is a constant factor ($2\times$) more than GD, but still linear in the cost of a single gradient call. The key idea is to use two adaptive perturbations per coordinate, evaluate their directional derivatives, and deterministically select a descent direction – all without computing second or higher order derivatives. There are two possibilities: 1. CPA could be used as an independent tool to assist escape of saddle points and, in particular, may escape saddle points more efficiently than Perturbed Gradient Descent (PGD).; 2. CPA could be a stand-alone algorithm for the whole optimization problem. We also define the Non-Descent Direction Approximation (NDDA) index as a cheap heuristic indicator of proximity to a local minimum for *deterministic optimization problems only*. Then, a 3-Gradient-Probe Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (3GCPA) is introduced for both *deterministic and probabilistic optimization problems*, which is also a constant factor ($3\times$) more than GD.

This note is a preliminary algorithmic description intended to establish priority. The algorithms are presented as heuristic tools; rigorous convergence guarantees are left for future work. Some experimental results for *deterministic optimization problems* are included in Sections 5 and 6 of the following preprint

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while the performance of CPA and 3GCPA at experiments of *probabilistic* ones (like machine learning and deep learning) are still under progress.

The source code is provided with that preprint. If any errors are discovered, the author would appreciate being notified by email at khcheng920911@gmail.com.

Note to the reader

The author’s background is in physics, not in formal optimization theory. Consequently, this work prioritizes a clear physical picture – treating the loss landscape as an energy landscape and using controlled perturbations to “feel” the local curvature – over mathematical rigor. The algorithm and the NDDA index are presented as *heuristic tools*. Formal guarantees, convergence rates, and detailed comparisons with state-of-the-art optimizers are left for future work.

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1 Background and motivation

Non-convex optimization lies at the heart of modern machine learning, signal processing, robotics, and many scientific computing applications. The loss landscapes in these domains are typically rugged, containing a multitude of critical points – local minima, local maxima, and saddle points. While local minima are desirable, saddle points can severely impede the convergence of first-order methods such as gradient descent (GD). At a strict saddle point, the gradient is zero but the Hessian possesses at least one negative eigenvalue, making it an unstable equilibrium. Near such points, GD stalls because it lacks directional information to descend further.

Classical strategies to escape saddle points include adding random noise (perturbed gradient descent, or PGD), using momentum, or leveraging second-order curvature information (e.g., trust-region methods, negative curvature search). Among these, PGD has gained popularity due to its simplicity and theoretical guarantees: by occasionally injecting isotropic Gaussian noise, it escapes strict saddles with high probability and converges to second-order stationary points. However, PGD has notable limitations:

- **Inefficiency of random kicks:** The perturbation direction is purely random. Many kicks may be wasted before a descent direction is accidentally found.
- **Difficulty with non-strict saddles:** When the Hessian is positive semi-definite (some eigenvalues zero), PGD often fails because there is no negative curvature to exploit; the algorithm may wander on a plateau for an extremely long time.
- **Lack of a cheap convergence indicator:** Standard stopping criteria rely on gradient norm, which does not distinguish between saddles and minima. Reliable detection of minima often requires Hessian information, which is computationally prohibitive in high dimensions.

These shortcomings motivate the need for a (semi-)deterministic, curvature-agnostic method that can (i) reliably identify a descent direction near saddles without relying on random chance, (ii) handle both strict and non-strict saddles, and (iii) provide an inexpensive, real-time measure of how close the iterate is to a local minimum.

2 Heuristic physical picture for Controlled Perturbation Algorithm for *deterministic optimization problems*

We first consider *deterministic optimization problems*. Suppose we would like to minimize a function $E(\theta)$, with dimension of θ being d . Suppose the system is at $\theta = \theta_0$. The idea of the Controlled Perturbation Algorithm is, for any i -th coordinate, an ε_i is chosen randomly. Gradient would then be computed at perturbed point $\theta_0 + \varepsilon$, whose sign on i -th coordinate would reflect whether the function is ascent or descent direction along the move ε_i in this direction. If it is descent, this direction would be our desired move. On the other hand, if the direction is ascent, we may consider its opposite direction. If this opposite direction is a descent one, this would be the desired direction. But if this direction is also ascent, it would be an indicator that the system may have a high chance in local minimum along this i -th coordinate. Therefore, we do not change the coordinate

in this direction.

Making use of the above idea, we propose the Non-Descent Direction Approximation (NDDA) Index on the ratio of non-descent directions in both forward and backward probes in *deterministic optimization problems* (For *probabilistic optimization problems*, like machine learning, the generalization to that cases remain an open question). In local minimum, this index would be expected to be close to 1.

A rigorous saddle point escape rate for the Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (CPA) is beyond the scope of this work. Nevertheless, we offer a heuristic argument for why its escape efficiency should be at least competitive with perturbed gradient descent (PGD) [4]. In PGD, a random perturbation is added uniformly in all directions to help the iterates leave saddle points. While this suffices to guarantee polynomial-time escape, a large fraction of the random directions may not correspond to descent directions in the local geometry, potentially requiring many attempts. In contrast, CPA uses an additional gradient evaluation to bias the perturbation toward directions of steepest descent. Therefore, we expect that CPA may waste fewer iterations on non-descent perturbations, and under similar smoothness conditions its escape efficiency may be at least as good as that of PGD. A formal Proof, or disproof, of this intuition is an interesting direction for future work.

Regarding the application of CPA, we currently have two proposals: 1. using them only once the system reaches a stationary point where the gradient vanishes. Specifically, CPA is applied to escape the stationary point, with, for *deterministic optimization problems*, the NDDA index serving as an indicator of whether a descent direction is present; after escape, the optimizer can switch to a traditional algorithm such as Adam or standard gradient descent. In this article, we only focus on the performance of CPA and PDG due to their similar nature. For comparison with other saddle point escape optimizers, it would be left for future investigation. 2. as a standalone optimizer for the whole optimization processes.

3 Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (CPA) for *deterministic optimization problems*

The following pseudocode describes the algorithm. Note that the computational cost is $O(d)$ per iteration, where d is the number of parameters (degrees of freedom).

Algorithm 1 Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (CPA)

Require: Objective function $E(\theta)$, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d$; initial parameters θ_0 ; amplification factor $\alpha \in [1.1, 2.0]$ (default 1.3); noise scale σ (or per-coordinate σ_i); max iterations K .

Ensure: θ_{final}

- 1: **for** $t = 0, \dots, K - 1$ **do**
- 2: Sample $\varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \text{diag}(\sigma_i^2))$ for each coordinate i .
- 3: Compute $I_{1,i} = \varepsilon_i \frac{\partial E}{\partial \theta_i} \Big|_{\theta_0 + \varepsilon}$ for every i .
- 4: Obtain ε'_i :

$$\varepsilon'_i = \begin{cases} \alpha \varepsilon_i & \text{if } I_{1,i} < 0 \\ -\varepsilon_i & \text{if } I_{1,i} > 0 \end{cases}$$

- 5: Compute the second index at $\theta_0 + \varepsilon'$:

$$I_{2,i} = \varepsilon'_i \frac{\partial E}{\partial \theta_i} \Big|_{\theta_0 + \varepsilon'}$$

- 6: **if** $I_{2,i} < 0$ **then**
 - 7: $\theta_{0,i} \leftarrow \theta_{0,i} + \varepsilon'_i$ ▷ Descent found along ε'
 - 8: **else if** $I_{1,i} < 0$ and $I_{2,i} > 0$ **then**
 - 9: $\theta_{0,i} \leftarrow \theta_{0,i} + \varepsilon_i$ ▷ Descent found only along original ε
 - 10: **else if** $I_{1,i} > 0$ and $I_{2,i} > 0$ **then**
 - 11: $\theta_{0,i} \leftarrow \theta_{0,i}$ ▷ No descent direction in this coordinate
 - 12: **end if**
 - 13: **end for**
 - 14: **return** θ_{final}
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Remark: The case $I_{1,i} = 0$ or $I_{2,i} = 0$ is extremely unlikely with random perturbations and continuous gradients; in practice we treat zero as non-descent (no update).

4 Non-Descent Direction Approximation (NDDA) Index for *deterministic optimization problems*

For *deterministic optimization problems*, where there is no intrinsic noise, the NDDA index is a heuristic indicator of how many coordinates behave like they are at a local minimum. It is computed by the same two perturbations but without performing any parameter update.

It has to be reminded that, in *probabilistic cases*, like most machine learning cases, the samples may have probabilistic fluctuation, which makes the index not close to 1 even if local minimum is achieved.

Algorithm 2 NDDA Index

Require: Objective function $E(\theta)$, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d$; current parameters θ_0 ; amplification factor α ; noise scale σ .

Ensure: NDDA $\in [0, 1]$

- 1: Sample $\varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \text{diag}(\sigma_i^2))$.
 - 2: Compute $I_{1,i} = \varepsilon_i \left. \frac{\partial E}{\partial \theta_i} \right|_{\theta_0 + \varepsilon}$.
 - 3: Obtain ε'_i as in CPA.
 - 4: Compute $I_{2,i} = \varepsilon'_i \left. \frac{\partial E}{\partial \theta_i} \right|_{\theta_0 + \varepsilon'}$.
 - 5: NDDA = $\frac{\#\{i | I_{1,i} \geq 0 \text{ and } I_{2,i} \geq 0\}}{d}$
 - 6: **return** NDDA
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For *deterministic optimization problems*, when NDDA ≈ 1 , the algorithm suggests that for most coordinates neither perturbation direction leads to a descent – this is consistent with being near a local minimum (or a very flat region). Conversely, low NDDA values indicate that many coordinates still have a detectable descent direction, which typically occurs near saddle points or on slopes.

Remark on perturbation magnitude choices

1. Diminishing parameters: start with a relatively large σ to escape saddles quickly, then decrease it gradually to fine-tune near a minimum.
2. Data-driven scaling: for neural networks, one can pass a batch of data through the model, compute the mean and standard deviation of each layer’s output, and set σ_i proportional to those statistics to keep perturbations in a natural range.

5 3-Gradient-Probe Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (3GCPA) for *deterministic and probabilistic optimization problems*

The author attempted to apply CPA (introduced in Section 3) to probabilistic models such as neural networks. However, CPA could not even match the performance of ordinary optimizers, leading the author to suspect that CPA may be limited to deterministic optimization problems. In stochastic optimization problems (e.g., machine learning and deep learning), the inherent noise in mini-batch samples renders judgments based solely on the sign of gradients unreliable. To address this issue specifically at saddle points, the author extended CPA by adding one more gradient evaluation, resulting in the 3-Gradient-Probe Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (3GCPA).

In 3GCPA, we first run CPA to identify a likely descent direction as suggested by the original algorithm. Instead of directly moving the parameters to the perturbed point, we compute the gradient at that point. As the gradient is computed near the unperturbed point, its direction would not be large. So in the worst case scenario where the non-descent directions are found in the CPA steps, we would at most push the system uphill, which may return to the original point by later gradient update. Moreover, there

is a possibility that the directions found by CPA steps are computed using one batch and the last gradient update on the unperturbed point is by another batch.

Another advantage of 3GCPA over CPA is the choice of magnitude of the perturbations. A natural way to choose the scales of the perturbations is the magnitude of the random perturbation to be chosen as a constant proportion (e.g. 0.1) of the weights themselves. However, in CPA, since the update is directly the perturbation, such choice would lead to the problem that the sign of the weights may not be altered in the updates. On the other hand, in 3GCPA, using the above method of choosing the magnitude of the perturbations would not lead to such problems as the ultimate updates of the parameters are the gradients at the perturbed points, which do not confine the sign of the weights.

We could also integrate 3GCPA with Adam (Hybrid 3GCPA-Adam). This could be done simply by replacing the gradient in Adam at the unperturbed point to the perturbed ones.

For justification of the above claim, the author runs the Cifar-10 experiment, the preliminary tests show that 3GCPA, Hybrid 3GCPA-Adam and traditional Adam achieved test accuracy of around 0.7 ± 0.01 , while CPA only got 0.65. However, since the model encountered seems to have no saddle points, this experiment could only be used as a proof of concept that 3GCPA-Adam could be used as a standalone optimizer.

Since 3GCPA-Adam involves 2 more gradient probes per iterations than Adam, it would be an open question of whether this hybrid model would converge as fast as the Adam alone. So the most conservative use of 3GCPA is only when arriving at stationary points. Once escape from saddle points, one could switch back to the original standardized optimizers.

Algorithm 3 3-Gradient-Probe Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (3GCPA)

Require: Objective function $E(\theta)$, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d$; initial parameters θ_0 ; amplification factor $\alpha \in [1.1, 2.0]$ (default 1.3); learning rate $lr = 0.001$; noise scale σ (or per-coordinate σ_i , which may be proportional to θ_i); max iterations K .

Ensure: θ_{final}

1: **for** $t = 0, \dots, K - 1$ **do**

2: Sample $\varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \text{diag}(\sigma_i^2))$ for each coordinate i .

3: Compute $I_{1,i} = \varepsilon_i \left. \frac{\partial E}{\partial \theta_i} \right|_{\theta_0 + \varepsilon}$ for every i .

4: Obtain ε'_i :

$$\varepsilon'_i = \begin{cases} \alpha \varepsilon_i & \text{if } I_{1,i} < 0 \\ -\varepsilon_i & \text{if } I_{1,i} > 0 \end{cases}$$

5: Compute the second index at $\theta_0 + \varepsilon'$:

$$I_{2,i} = \varepsilon'_i \left. \frac{\partial E}{\partial \theta_i} \right|_{\theta_0 + \varepsilon'}$$

6: Find the perturbed point θ_1 :

7: **if** $I_{2,i} < 0$ **then**

8: $\theta_{1,i} \leftarrow \theta_{0,i} + \varepsilon'_i$ ▷ Descent found along ε'

9: **else if** $I_{1,i} < 0$ and $I_{2,i} > 0$ **then**

10: $\theta_{1,i} \leftarrow \theta_{0,i} + \varepsilon_i$ ▷ Descent found only along original ε

11: **else if** $I_{1,i} > 0$ and $I_{2,i} > 0$ **then**

12: $\theta_{1,i} \leftarrow \theta_{0,i}$ ▷ No descent direction in this coordinate

13: **end if**

14: Update the θ_0 as:

15: $\theta_{0,i} \leftarrow \theta_{0,i} - lr \left. \frac{\partial E}{\partial \theta_i} \right|_{\theta_1}$ ▷ Note that the gradient is computed at θ_1 , not θ_0

16: **end for**

17: **return** θ_{final}

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Patent Notice

The algorithm CPA has been filed as a PCT patent application, Application No.: PCT/CN2026/092722, with a filing date of 24 April 2026.

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